

Dendrochronological analysis of Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway

C6131

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CATS dendro report 11 (2nd June 2015)

In this report, the dendrochronological analysis of the two reliefs of the Borre altarpiece, Norway, is described. This research was commissioned to contribute to the research project, 'After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550'. The project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO).

Fig. 1. Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway. The reliefs are taken out of their later framing, to enable examination of the backs of the carvings.

The altarpiece (fig. 1) consists of two reliefs, carved in oak (*Quercus sp.*), set into a frame of conifer wood (probably pine (*Pinus sp.*)) but this was not examined

microscopically to confirm this). A date of 1635 is painted at the top of the conifer frame, but the two oak reliefs are assumed to be earlier, having originally belonged to a larger composition.

The two oak reliefs were removed from the frame to enable examination of the back of these carvings. The fronts of these are shown in figs. 2 and 3 and, as can be seen, a lot of the polychromy is preserved. The composition of the carving, where the figures depicted, all move towards the right, strongly suggests that these two reliefs were originally part of a much larger scene.

Observations

On examination of the back of the reliefs, which are much more roughly carved than the fronts (fig. 3), it could be confirmed that the wood on both reliefs are oak. It was also noted that the tree-rings on the wood of both carvings are rather wide. This indicates that we are dealing with very fast growing trees. The possibility for a successful dendrochronological dating and provenance determination for the work was therefore very limited. However, macro photographs of the surface were taken, for subsequent tree-ring measurement, not just to document the wood used, but also to examine the possibility that the two reliefs had been fashioned from the same tree. The anatomical layout of the wood suggested namely that the two reliefs were sculpted from an oak log that had been split in half.

Fig. 2. Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway. The front of the reliefs.

Fig. 3. Borre reliefs, Norway (right-hand-side relief). The back of the carvings are roughly finished allowing examination of the tool marks and the wood anatomy.

Another observation that was made, on examination of the backs of the Borre reliefs, was that the well preserved tool marks feature a very marked signature (fig. 4), caused by small nicks in the cutting edge of the axe used. The same signature was observed on both reliefs, indicating that the same tool was used to shape the backs of both pieces, again indicating their production in one work process.

Measurements

Measuring of oak for dendrochronology conventionally entails access to the transverse section of the wood. In the case of artworks on oak, this is done by gently cleaning or paring the object to expose the rings. Dendrochronology of art objects is always carried out with minimum damage to the object.

In the case of the two Borre reliefs, the tree-rings were readily visible throughout the angular surface of the backs. The tree-ring measurements could be reliably taken with absolutely no preparation of the wood, and were thus completely non-invasively acquired, by taking macro photographs of the surfaces, along with a ruler for scale. These photos were then stitched together using Adobe Photoshop (version 11.0.2), and measured using an application “Able Image Analyser” (fig. 5). The scale is used to calibrate the picture, but due to the unconventional angles by which the tree-rings

were visible, the measurements in this case are not wholly to a defined scale, particularly at the inner rings. Nevertheless, the relative annual ring widths can be recorded, as can be seen in the plot of the resulting measurements (fig 6), and it is the annual variation that is the key to dendrochronological analysis. For calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997).

Fig. 4. Borre reliefs, Norway. Wide tree-rings are clearly visible on the back of the oak carvings. Very marked tool signatures can also be seen and the same signature appears on the back of both the right and left reliefs.

The results

Tree-ring measurements were made on both reliefs. The left hand side relief contains 58 rings while the right hand side piece contains 65 rings. Only heartwood is preserved, all the sapwood having been trimmed away during the carving of the pieces. The tree-ring curves match together at the relative position illustrated in the plot of the curves (fig. 6), achieving a t -value at this position of $t = 7.66$, with an overlap of 58 years.

When identifying elements that might come from the same tree, using dendrochronology, usually two tree-ring curves should achieve t -values greater than $t = 10$, but this is when the material being analysed is from long-lived trees, with tree-ring series of over 100 rings. However, evaluating whether material is from the same tree does not rely on the statistical correlation alone, but also on a visual comparison of the tree-ring curves, as is shown here in fig. 6. The similarity of the tree-ring curves from the two Borre reliefs, coupled with the high t -value at a quite short overlap, and with observations of the wood of the two carvings, allows the conclusion that the two were most probably made from two halves of the same log.

Fig. 5. Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway. Measuring of the tree-rings is carried out on screen from macro photographs, using the program “Able Image Analyzer”. No markings are made on the actual object. The red lines are made on screen, and mark every 10th ring while the white lines are marking each ring width. A ruler for scale allows calibration of the photo and measurements, in 100ths of a millimetre, are recorded in a simple spreadsheet.

Conclusion

In spite of the fact that the two oak pieces from the Borre altarpiece contained insufficient tree-rings to enable dating of the trees used for the carvings, much information could be attained from examination of the wood anatomy of the reliefs. Examination of the backs revealed that the reliefs were both carved from half logs, and the tree-ring patterns support the possibility that they were from the same log. Tool marks from the shaping of the backs, preserving identical axe signatures, also indicate that at least some of the shaping of the pieces was done with the same tool.

The very fast rate of growth that this oak exhibits is not characteristic of the Southern Baltic oaks that we so often see in art objects, where fine straight-grained panelling and planking dominates. As it is not possible to date the felling of the tree that was used for the Borre reliefs, it is of course not possible to determine the region in which the tree grew either. Given the very fast rate of growth of the tree, it can be suggested however, that this tree grew in an open landscape, where it did not need to compete with neighbouring trees for access to light.

Fig. 6. Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway. Diagram showing the relative position of the two tree-ring curves. The tree-ring patterns are so similar, it could indicate that the two reliefs were made from the same tree.

Literature

Baillie, M.G.L. and Pilcher, J.R., 1973: A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bulletin* 33, 7-14.

Tyers, I.G., 1997. Dendro for Windows Program Guide, *ARCUS Report* 340, Sheffield.

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z132001a	Borre altarpiece relief left side	58			O	V	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z1320029	Borre altarpiece relief right side	65			O	V	0	N	H1	H1	undated
	Averages (same tree)										
Z132S001	Borre altarpiece relief 2 timbers	65			O	V	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
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Table 1. Borre altarpiece, two reliefs, Norway. List of objects analysed.